

Magma Source, pre-eruptive dynamics and timescales of major explosions at Stromboli volcano (Italy)

Supplementary figures for Bulletin of Volcanology

Laura Insinga^{1*}, Marija Voloschina², Paola Marianelli², Erika Bartolomeo², Antonella Bertagnini³, Nicole Métrich⁴, Silvio G. Rotolo^{1,5}, Alessandro Aiuppa¹, Maurizio Ripepe⁶, Marco Pistolesi²

¹Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra e del Mare, Università di Palermo, Palermo (Italy).

²Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra, Università di Pisa, Pisa (Italy).

³Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Sezione di Pisa, Pisa (Italy).

⁴Université Paris-Cité, Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris, CNRS, Paris (France)

⁵ Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Sezione di Palermo, Palermo (Italy).

⁶ Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra, Università di Firenze, Florence (Italy).

*Corresponding author email address: laura.insinga@unipa.it

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Fig. S1: Additional transmitted light microphotographs of olivine phenocrysts and melt inclusions from the 24 November 2009 major explosion. The images on the right are zoomed-in sections of images on the left.

Fig. S2: K_2O vs. SiO_2 (wt.%) diagram (Ewart, 1982) plotting glassy groundmass (Mtx) and melt inclusion (MI) composition of different major explosions (ME) at Stromboli: 23 August and 24 November 1998 (Landi et al. 2022), 3 May, 8 and 24 November 2009 (this study), 19 July 2020 (Voloschina et al. 2023). For the 2009 major explosions, the average error for SiO_2 and K_2O are less than 1% and 1%, respectively.

Fig. S3: CaO/Al₂O₃ in glassy groundmass (Mtx) or embayments (Emb) vs. Fo rim (wt.%) of major explosions and paroxysms: 3 May 2009 major explosion (this study, La Felice and Landi 2011), 8 and 24 November 2009 major explosions (this study), 19 July 2020 (Voloschina et al. 2023), 15 March 2007 small-scale paroxysm (Métrich et al. 2010) and historic large-scale paroxysm (Bertagnini et al. 2003). Cross symbols indicate glassy groundmass, empty dots indicate embayments. Average errors (CaO/Al₂O₃ = 1%; Fo rim less than 1%) are indicated as error bars. ME = major explosion; SSP = small-scale paroxysm; LSP = large-scale paroxysm.

Fig. S4: Dissolved H₂O contents (wt.%) in olivine-hosted melt inclusions and associated Fo rim (mol%) from the 3 May, 8 November and 24 November 2009 major explosions (ME). Note that the high-H₂O melt inclusions of the 24 November event are located in olivine crystals with strong reverse zoning. Average error relative to Fo rim (less than 1%) and maximum error for H₂O (13%) are indicated as error bars.

Fig S5: H₂O vs. K₂O in melt inclusions from the 2009 major explosions (ME). Average error relative to K₂O (1%) and maximum error for H₂O (13%) are indicated as error bars. HP = high porphyritic.

Fig. S6: H₂O/K₂O vs. CaO/Al₂O₃ in melt inclusions (MI) and embayments (Emb) from the ordinary activity (Scoria 1999; Métrich et al. 2010), 3 May, 8 November and 24 November 2009 major explosions (this study), 19 July 2020 major explosion (Voloschina et al. 2023), 5 April 2003 and 15 March 2007 small-scale paroxysms (Métrich et al. 2005, 2010), historic large-scale paroxysm (Bertagnini et al. 2003). Maximum error for H₂O/K₂O (13%) and average error for CaO/Al₂O₃ (1%) for the 3 May, 8 November and 24 November 2009 data are indicated as error bars. ME = major explosion; SSP = small-scale paroxysm; LSP = large-scale paroxysm.

Fig. S7: Cl vs. H₂O in melt inclusions (MI) and embayments (Emb) from the 3 May, 8 November and 24 November 2009 major explosions (this study), 5 April 2003 and 15 March 2007 small-scale paroxysms (Métrich et al. 2005, 2010), historic large-scale paroxysm (Bertagnini et al. 2003). Maximum error for H₂O (13%) and average error for Cl (5% for the November events, 9% for the 3 May event) for the 3 May, 8 November and 24 November 2009 are indicated as error bars. See legend in Fig. S5.

Fig. S8: H₂O, CO₂, S and Cl vs. MgO in melt inclusions (MI) from the 3 May, 8 November and 24 November 2009 major explosions (this study), 19 July 2020 major explosion (Voloschina et al. 2023), 5 April 2003 and 15 March 2007 small-scale paroxysms (Métrich et al. 2005, 2010), historic large-

scale paroxysm (Métrich et al. 2010). Maximum error for H₂O and CO₂ (13%) and average error for MgO (2%), S (31%) and Cl (5% for the November events, 9% for the 3 May) for the 3 May, 8 November and 24 November 2009 data are indicated as error bars. ME = major explosion; SSP = small-scale paroxysm; LSP = large-scale paroxysm.

Fig. S9: H₂O vs. FeO in melt inclusions (MI) from the 3 May, 8 November and 24 November 2009 major explosions (this study), 19 July 2020 major explosion (Voloschina et al. 2023), 5 April 2003 and 15 March 2007 small-scale paroxysms (Métrich et al. 2005, 2010), historic large-scale paroxysm (Métrich et al. 2010). Maximum error for H₂O (13%) and FeO (2%) for the 3 May, 8 November and 24 November 2009 are indicated as error bars. ME = major explosion; SSP = small-scale paroxysm; LSP = large-scale paroxysm.

Fig. S10: Comparison between uncorrected and PEC-corrected SiO₂, MgO and FeO in melt inclusions from this study. Only a minor subset of melt inclusions from the 2009 major explosions is affected by PEC. The dashed black line represents the 1:1 ratio, deviations from this line reflect the effect of PEC correction. Note that major element ratios as those reported in in Figs. 3 and 4 are not affected by PEC (Rose-Koga et al. 2021).

Fig. S11: Timescale results calculated in DIPRA from Fe-Mg diffusion profiles in olivine phenocrysts. Best fit to forsterite natural data (C = concentration in olivine reported as mol fraction) are shown in red lines. Natural data (black line) together with initial conditions (purple line) and orientation of Fe-Mg traverse in olivine are reported. Numbers in olivines indicate olivine composition in mol %. Continued.

